

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

Exploring Human Society and Culture
in a Global Context

International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities

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International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (IJSSH) is dedicated to exploring human behavior, culture, values, and institutions, as well as the social, political, and historical contexts that shape them. It seeks to generate knowledge that not only advances academic understanding but also contributes to solving real-world problems, promoting critical reflection, and fostering more inclusive, equitable societies.

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Original Research Paper

Evaluating the Impact of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments on the Organisational Performance of Listed African Financial and Non-Financial Firms

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Abstract: This investigation seeks to evaluate the impact of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments on organizational performance in the financial and non-financial firms in the listed African country. The numerical facts for investigations consisted of mostly qualitative data primarily acquired through employee interviews. While there was some quantitative data collected, the effectiveness of organizational decisions. More also, It is significant to note that the study is not an exclusive investigation of issues. However, Result of the study revealed that there is no relationship between selection on employees' value adding or turnover and firms performance of financial and non-financial firms in Africa. Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments on the Organisational Performance of Listed African Financial and Non-Financial Firms can curb fraudulent practices in African financial and non-financial firms and Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments can help in detecting and preventing fraud in the firms across Africa. The listed policy suggestion emerges; Africans) people should ignore political instability, economic mismanagement, corruption and other negative factors on Nigeria Africans financial and non-financial economy and There should be a reward set aside for those who successfully report fraudulent practices after due examination that the report given was authentic and the issue of fraud was duly carried out or was about to be carried out.

Keywords: Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments; Organizational Performance; Financial and Non-Financial Firms; African

Introduction

Cyber forensics helps prevent future cyber-attacks by identifying vulnerabilities, understanding attack methods, and providing insights that can be used to strengthen security measures. The application of cyberforensic accounting

in fraud detection and evaluation has become more feasible due to the globalized globe. While, Organizational performance is related to organizational justice, which allows employees to get committed to task assigned to him or her. There has been offensive increase in financial fraud in the corporate world and Government agencies

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in Nigeria, from the politicians to the bank directors/executives, from the legal officers to the law enforcement personnel, from the civil servants to the school teacher, from the trader in the market to the hawkers on the street, the tendency for fraud and fraud related crimes is endless. On the other hand, Organizations are becoming more aware of important role Forensic Planning Investments play in the success of their organizations to achieve financial performance.

As a result, organizations are becoming more employee-centric by focusing on enhancing employees' engagement and organizational commitment

It is significant for organization to adopt Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments system that optimizes workforce as it enables organization to achieve competitive advantage in today's global market economy that provides wider access to technology, finance and other resources.

However, with the application of forensic accounting, fraud may be easily detected, controlled and reduced to a very minimal level. Having considerable impact on the performance of organizations and these contribute to the affirmative link between Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments and organizational performance (Osman, 2012).

Forensic accounting is said to bring significant improvement in the quality of fraud detection and prevention.

This study is meant to help and remind the Local governments in Lagos States to design an integrated approach to preventing and controlling of fraud and corruption within the work place through an established service of professional forensic accountants.

The Africa financial industry is managed and controlled by the Africa Reserve Bank (ARB) as the regulatory authority over the banking industry and financial institutions, aiming to achieve a robust and efficient

banking system in the interest of the customers and the economy in accordance with the Banks Act (No. 94 of 1990), or the Mutual Banks Act (No. 124 of 1993) (ARB, 2020).

Information Technology (IT) is critical in succeeding this ambition and for performing the day-to-day organization operations for most firms (Ali et al., 2017:70). Nevertheless, it can be said that IT has an adverse impact on the financial and non- financial industry in Africa, too, where crimes like phishing, hacking, forgery etc. are committed (Ramadani et al., 2018:341).

Cyber- corruption involving the use of malicious software, computer hacking and denial-of-service attacks, phishing, data theft, spamming, card theft, online fraud, phishing, spying, etc. are becoming more common (Tiwari et al., 2016:47-50; Cassim 2016:131; Ali et al., 2017:72-73).

To evaluate the impact of cyber forensic architecture investments, track key performance indicators (KPIs) like reduced incident resolution times, successful forensic investigation outcomes (fraud identification), and improved security posture. Assess improvements in tangible metrics such as financial loss reduction and increased shareholder trust, as well as intangible benefits like enhanced public confidence and regulatory compliance. Use a holistic approach like the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework to consider how technology, organizational factors, and external environment contribute to overall cyber security and by extension, of organization performance

Statement of the Problem

Recently, series of financial frauds have been perpetuated in various sectors of the economy and the world at large. These financial frauds have led to the collapse of many reputable institutions and loss of huge amount of investments as seen in the cases of some listed African financial and non-financial firms like Savana Bank Plc.,

Habib Bank Plc., Oceanic Bank Plc., Enron, Cadbury, Worldcom, Dunlop, etc. These cases of financial frauds however, have been perpetuated under the close supervision of internal control officers. It suffices to say that the independence of the internal auditor is not guaranteed because he works as an employee of the government or an organization. This led to the introduction of external auditors, yet frauds are still not reduced.

The similitude of this is the case of the Financial and Non-Financial Firms in Africa, where officials made an unauthorized excess expenditure totaling \$15 million in 2012, just as 52 payment vouchers amounting to \$30.2 million and duly paid and posted in the treasury cashbook, was not produced for audit verification (Micheal, 2014).

The general difficult addressed was the impact of lesser investments in cyber security by smaller organizations resulting in a greater susceptibility to organized cyber-attacks.

The Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) has also been established in Africa to respond swiftly to incidences of cybercrime.

Takahashi et al. (2018) stated that one of the primary challenges to organizations is cyber security and access to timely and actionable information is critical for thwarting attacks. Chronopoulos et al. (2018) highlighted how organizations are unable to secure their information systems due to ineffective security investment decisions. Fielder et al. (2016) indicated that organizations are unable to effectively invest in resources to combat the threat of attackers due to weak decision-making strategies as related to cyber security.

The mounting list of fraud in Nigeria has also stirred the attention of the government to set up agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) to investigate the

occurrences of financial fraud. Despite the effort, the prevalence of financial fraud is yet at the increases (Popoola, Che-Ahmad, Samsudin, Salleh, & Babatunde, 2016).

The supremacy of the Buhari led administration is the fight against corruption and insecurity. Huge amount of funds have been recovered, many arrests have been made; however, the number of prosecution cannot be viewed in the same manner.

It now become pertinent that forensic accounting be introduced and practices since the external auditors may not have the required training to be able to tackle modern frauds like white collar crimes such as security fraud, embezzlement, bankruptcies, internet fraud and contract disputes. These areas have become a complex area of concern for the accounting profession.

Research Objective

The foremost objective of this study is to discover or evaluate the impact of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments on organizational performance. Aside this, other specific objectives that will be addresses are;

- i. To examine the relationship between Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments and selection on employees' value adding or turnover.
- ii. To examine the effect of organizational performance on of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments.
- iii. To recommend, to policy formulators factors that can enhance performance on of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments

Research Hypothesis

- i. **H0₁:** There is significant effect on organizational performance and of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial and non-financial firms in Africa.

- ii. **H0₂**: there is relationship between Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments and selection on employees' value adding or turnover and firms performance of financial and non-financial firms in Africa

Significance of the Study

This investigation will be of significant of interest to the financial and non-financial firms, the government of most African country's as there are almost to diversify our economic into other strategic planning to become one of the world leading sustainability economies in the year 2030 and the other firms or institute at large.

The motivation for this study is a noted fact for any meaningful economic transformation of most country in "Africa" there is a need to determine or measure economic status, position and strength and to formulate future strategy in economic, financial and non- financial Africa firms.

Scope of the Study

The investigation will aid in laying a solid framework for the design and implementation of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments practices of financial and non- financial Africa firms. Since cyber forensic accounting is still new in developing Africa countries, this study will aid policy makers and other stakeholders to draft adequate policies to guide the practice of cyber forensic accounting of financial and non-financial. The study will also serve as a guide to financial and non-financial practicing firms and independent researchers who may have interest in the issue matter. Findings from this study will serve as a guide in carrying out other research studies in cyber forensic accounting of financial and non-financial organizations.

Literature Review

This study reviews the literature of the research. It consists of Conceptual Review, Theoretical framework. The review will convey greatly on fact and figures obtained from purchased published reference

materials such as books, online publications and journals. The evaluation will provide an overview of foremost evidence on past activities that had earlier been studied in relation to the research (Ramonu, 2023).

Concepts of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments

In a bid to reducing fraud and corruption all over the world, countries have been setting up anti-crime agencies to investigate issues of fraud and white collar crimes. It is in no doubt that corruption has ruined the economy of many countries in the world and lots of investments have been lost by stakeholders as a result of this. This has led to the introduction of Forensic Accounting.

Many scholars have defined the term "Forensic Accounting" in different ways. In most of the corporate organizations, forensic accounting investigation is widely seen as a mechanism that provides more comprehensive details information concerning financial fraud (Eliezer & Emmanuel, 2015; Efofa & Kingsley, 2016).

Popoola et al., (2016) consider forensic accounting as a process of using accounting skills and knowledge to investigate fraud or misappropriation of fund and to analyze the financial information for use in legal proceedings. Eze (2015) noted that Forensic accounting involve investigative accounting and litigation that have to do with any wrong doing found during or after activities involved in organizations.

According to Okoye and Gbegi (2013), forensic accounting is the application of accounting knowledge and investigative skills to identify and resolve legal issues. It serves as assistance in disputes: Which are likely to involve litigation, arbitration, expert determination, mediation or an enquiry by an appropriate regulatory authority, and investigation of suspected frauds, irregularity or impropriety which could potentially lead to civil, criminal or disciplinary proceedings; while focusing primarily on accounting issues.

Modugu and Ayaduba (2013) defined Forensic accounting as the tripartite practice of utilizing accounting, auditing and investigative skills to assist in legal matters. Adegbe and Fakile (2012) described forensic accounting as the application of investigative and analytical skills in a manner that meets standards required by courts of law.

Singleton and Singleton (2010), defined forensic accounting as the comprehensive view of fraud investigation. It includes preventing frauds and analyzing anti-fraud control which includes the gathering of non-financial information. Dhar and Sarkar (2010) defined forensic accounting as the application of accounting concepts and techniques to legal problems. It demands reporting, where accountability of the fraud is established and the report is considered as evidence in the court of law or in administrative proceedings.

Forensic accounting has been pivotal in the public sector after the financial reporting problems which took place in some local governments in Lagos State, Nigeria. For instance, these scandals resulted in the loss of public trust and huge amounts of money. In order to avoid fraud and theft, and to restore the badly needed public confidence, public sectors need to take the step to improve the infrastructure of their internal control and accounting systems drastically. This development will increase the importance of accountants who have chosen to specialize in forensic accounting and who are consequently referred as forensic accountants.

Fraud and Fraud Detection

Many scholars have defined Fraud in several ways. However, It's important to note that defining fraud is as difficult as identifying it. No definite and invariable rule can be laid down as a general proposition in defining fraud as it includes surprise, trick, cunning and unfair ways by which another is cheated.

According to CIMA (2009), and Suleiman et al. (2018), word fraud usually consists of

actions such as partaking in stealing, collusion, money laundering, dishonesty, bribery, extortion, abuse of office, insider trading and misappropriation of the assets.

Fraud is a generic category of criminal conduct that involve the use of dishonest or deceitful means in order to obtain some unjust advantage or gain over another (Okoye, Maimako, Jugu, & Jat, 2017). Fraud is the number one enemy of business growth all over the world. It is a global phenomenon that has been in existence for long and it increases day by day (Inaya&Isito, 2016).

Fraud refers to anything calculated to deceive, whether by a single act or combination, or by suppression of the truth, or suggestion of what is false, whether it is by direct falsehood, by speech or silence, word of mouth, look or gesture (Saidu, 2015).

Nwaze (2012) defined fraud as a predetermined as well as planned tricky process or device usually undertaken by a person or group of persons with the sole aim of cheating another person or organisation to gain ill-gotten advantage which would not have accrued in the absence of such deceptive procedure.

Over time, the importance of initial detection of fraud has increased because the number of fraudulent events has increased. Detection of fraud begins with the notification of red flags which indicates that something is wrong (Ozkul and Pamukc, 2012). This might come to light as a result of trends in the number of employees, managers, and victims concerned about the loss in business assets. There are two main ways to detect frauds: (a) Detection by chance and (b) Conducting a proactive research and encouraging initial identification of symptoms. Many fraudulent acts have been detected in the past by chance. Unfortunately, the incidence of fraud proceeds during detection and losses consequently increase. In many cases, people who are exposed to fraud in the organization do know that

fraud was being committed, but could not bring it to light either because they are not sure and unwilling to blame someone directly or are unsure of how to go about reporting it and might also be afraid of being labelled as whistleblower (Ozkul and Pamukc, 2012).

Accounting fraud is an act of knowingly falsifying accounting records, such as sales or cost records, in order to boost the net income or sales figures; accounting fraud is illegal and subjects the company and the executives involved to civil lawsuits (Arokiasamy and Cristal, 2009).

Types of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments and Fraud

White-collar fraud involves an intentional deception, by employees, management, owners, members, volunteers, vendors, customers, and anyone else with any relationship or association to a business, to inappropriately obtain money or other assets or services from a business. Some frauds are perpetrated by individuals, and some occur in collusion across the management-employee social boundaries or between insiders and outsiders. The most useful way to classify the activity of the fraudster is to discuss briefly the four accounting cycles common within any business. The four cycles are as follows:

1. Sales and Collections/Receipts
2. Purchases and Payments (Disbursements)
3. Personnel and Payroll
4. Inventory and Warehousing

1. Sales and Collections/Receipts Cycle

The sales and collections cycle involves invoicing customers or clients for sales of goods or services while payments can be made immediately or at a future date. This cycle is the most cash-intensive of the five cycles, with the access and opportunity to divert customer payments (cash and other forms) at greatest risk. Some of the common fraud schemes perpetrated within this cycle are: Include theft of cash or other

customer payments, theft of other assets, kickbacks to customers and front-end frauds.

2. Purchases and Payments (Disbursements) Cycle

This cycle includes the purchasing of and payments for goods, equipment, and services used in an organization's operations. Through this cycle a number of schemes could occur, within the purchasing process as well as the payment process. Payments may be made by an organization through traditional means, such as by cash or more likely cheque, or could be in the form of electronic payments. Payments may be completed by telephone or via online access through the organization's banking systems, and can even be made using common hand-held wireless devices found in many of today's business environments. An individual working within purchasing may act alone by setting up shell companies to receive goods misdirected from the company by false invoices, or may collude with other individuals if segregated duties prevent the first individual from both approving and processing unauthorized transactions.

3. Personnel and Payroll Cycle

This cycle comprises hiring, maintaining, and terminating employees; establishing salary and benefit amounts; maintaining timekeeping; tracking and approving employee expense reimbursements; and all other aspects relating to compensating employees. The personnel process incorporates recruiting, screening, and hiring procedures, to ensure proper backgrounds and verification measures are completed with each and every new hire. Common fraud schemes perpetrated within this cycle include paying ghost employees (fictitious employees on the system that do not exist), paying terminated employees beyond their termination date and diverting their paychecks, overstating hours worked, overstating expenses incurred and submitted for reimbursement, and filing false medical claims, to list a few.

4. Inventory and Warehousing Cycle

This cycle controls the purchase and storage of goods for later processing and sale, or for direct sale. The most common frauds in this cycle are: ordering unnecessary or excess inventory, and then stealing it for personal use; committing outright theft of inventory; and charging embezzlements occurring elsewhere in the company to inventory losses.

Obstacles to Effective Prosecution of Corrupt Practices and Financial Crimes in Nigeria

According to Ribadu (2004), he stated that corruption and other economic crimes are the bane of Nigeria economic development efforts. Therefore, all the crimes are harmful to the economy in no small measures.

Those who are saddled with the responsibility of fighting crimes will do well if they do not compromise, thereby making corruption a little monster to be crushed with ease. He however, outlined the following factors that affected the prosecuting of criminals:

- a) Cooperation from persons/institutions who should furnish relevant information.
- b) The quality of evidence gathered at the investigation stage.
- c) The transparency of investigation of the case itself.
- d) The prosecutorial competes of the prosecuting counsel.
- e) The transparency and fairness of the presiding judge in the trail.
- f) Inadequacy of existing procedural and evidence laws.
- g) Congestion and slow pace of court proceedings.
- h) Jurisdiction problems.
- i) Cost of investigation and prosecution.

Approaches to a Forensic Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments Assignment

Each forensic accounting assignment is unique. Accordingly, the actual approach adopted and the procedures performed will be specific to it. Eiyal, Otalor and Awili (2013) states that the steps Forensic Accounting assignments will include:

1. Meet With The Client:

It is helpful to meet with the client to obtain an understanding of the important facts, players and issues at hand.

2. Perform A Conflict Check:

A conflict check should be carried out as soon as the relevant parties are established.

3. Perform An Initial Investigation:

It is often useful to carry out a preliminary investigation prior to the development of a detailed plan of action. This will allow subsequent planning to be based upon a more complete understanding of the issues.

4. Develop An Action Plan:

This plan will take into account the knowledge gained by meeting with the client and carrying out the initial investigation and will set out the objectives to be achieved and the methodology to be utilized to accomplish them.

5. Obtain The Relevant Evidence:

Depending on the nature of the case this may involve locating documents, economic information, assets, a person or company, another expert or proof of the occurrence of an event.

6. Perform The Analysis:

The actual analysis performed will be dependent upon the nature of the assignment and may involve:

- a) Calculating economic damages;
- b) Summarizing a large number of transactions;
- c) Performing a tracing of assets;

- d) Performing present value calculations utilizing appropriate discount rates;
- e) Performing a regression or sensitivity analysis;
- f) Utilizing a computerized application such as a spread sheet, data base or computer model; and
- g) Utilizing charts and graphics to explain the analysis.

Prepare The Report:

Often a report will be prepared which may include sections on the nature of the assignment, scope of the investigation, approach utilized, limitations of scope and findings and/or opinions. The report will include schedules and graphics necessary to properly support and explain the findings.

Empirical Review

Litigation is a term encompassing the use of court processes to resolve a dispute, in line with the rules in place in that jurisdiction (Dada and Jimoh, 2020). According to Harwood (2016), stages in litigation involves before litigation starts, preparing a case and finally, trial and enforcement. Before litigation begins various forms of preliminary investigations takes place also, various forms of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) are encouraged to be examined. It is encouraged that parties consider alternative means of resolving the disputes first. The more conventional Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) options include: Arbitration a confidential form of dispute resolution where one or more arbitrators decide a case rather than a court appointed judge. Mediation is a facilitated negotiation assisted by an independent third- party mediator appointed by the parties. An independent expert is appointed to resolve the matter by producing a legally binding decision (Harwood, 2016). In preparing cases for litigation claim forms and particulars of claims for both parties are drafted and served accordingly, this is usually followed by defence and counter

claims and replies by the parties involved. Allocations and directions for future conducts of the case are done, presentation of documents, statements by witnessing, expert reports and meetings with experts all form part of the preparation of cases for litigations. This stage is now followed by the trial and enforcement stage as well as appeals by the parties involved. The concept of litigation and business advisory adopted in this study is how the fear and possible avoidance of a court process as well as yielding to expert's objective and independent advice as a forensic accounting technique can serve as an instrument for mitigating as well as possible curbing of financial crimes in the public sector organizations by the perpetrators of these crimes (Harwood, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Fraud Triangle

The fraud triangle is what the forensic accountant rely on to identify suspected fraud, the causes and the weakness in the system that prompted the fraud. Based on the fraud triangle concept the three (3) factors that cumulate into the triangle are; incentive, opportunity, and rationalization. For any individual to be involved in a fraud he/she must have the incentive, opportunity and be rational.

Source: Kassem and Higson, 2021

1. Opportunity:

Employees use their position to commit fraud when internal controls are weak, or where there is poor management oversight on internal control implementation. Most Employees who commit fraud do so, because they have the opportunity to access assets and information that allows

them obscure their fraudulent deeds. It is true that employees need access to certain platform to perform their jobs. The same access can provide the employee with opportunity to commit fraud.

2. Pressure/Incentive:

Pressure can make a staff commit fraud. Pressure does not only mean financial pressure. Lister (2007), state that there are three types of motivation or pressure: Personal pressure to pay for lifestyle, employment pressure from continuous compensation structures, or management's financial interest, and external pressure such as threats to the business financial stability, financier covenants, and market expectations. The identified matters are what motivate an employee to commit fraud.

3. Rationalization:

Rationalization is an attempt by an employee to justify why they commit fraud. For instance an employee who is about to be evicted from his/her home, can be used to justify fraudulent act. The employee may say "I deserve to have a place to call my home." So also an employee who feels he/she is underpaid may say it is a way of augmenting the payment due to him/her. As such the rationalization is an act of employee who commits fraud to give reasons for his action. It is a way of covering up for the wrong done to the employer. By making the employers feel guilty of the circumstance.

Forensic accounting relies on the fraud triangle to identify weak points in the business systems and find possible suspects in cases of fraud. It consists of three core concepts which together create a situation ripe for fraud: incentive, opportunity, and rationalization. People must have the incentive and opportunity to commit financial fraud, as well as the ability to justify it. Recent analysis has suggested adding a fourth concept to make a diamond capability. Just because someone has the opportunity or incentive to steal does not necessarily mean that they have the capability to do so. For example, if

someone does not understand how to make journal or ledger entries in the books of accounts, they would not know how to manipulate numbers no matter what the incentive or opportunity is (Rasey 2009).

White Collar Crime Theory of Fraud

The basic theory that has been established in this research work is "white collar crime theory" by Sutherland (1949) as cited in Michael (2004). The term white-collar crime dates back to 1939. Sutherland (1949) as cited in Michael (2004) was the first to coin the term, and hypothesis white-collar criminals, attributed different characteristics and motives than typical street criminals.

Sutherland originally presented the theory in an address to the American Sociological Society in attempt to study two field, crime and high society which had no previous empirical correlation. Sutherland defined his idea as "crime committed by a person respectability and high social status in the course of his occupation" (Sutherland in Michael, 2004). Sutherland noted that in his time, less than two (2) percent of the persons committed to prison in a year belong to the upper class. Sutherland goal was to prove a relation between money, social status, and likelihood of going to jail for a white-collar crime, compared to more visible, typical crimes, although, the percentage is a bit higher today.

Much of Sutherlands work was to separate and define the difference in blue collar street crimes, such as arson, burglary, theft, assault, rape and vandalism which are often blamed on psychological, associational and structural factors. Instead, white-collar criminals are opportunists, who over time learn they can take advantage of their circumstances to accumulated financial gain. They are educated, intelligent, affluent, individuals who are qualified enough to get a job which allows them the unmonitored access to often large sum of money. But the federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) has adopted a narrow approach defining white-collar crime as those illegal acts which are characterized

by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust and which are not dependent upon the application or threat of physical force or violence. The blue-collar crime will more often use physical force, whereas, in the corporate world, the identification of a victim is less obvious and the issuer of reporting is complicated by a culture of commercial confidentiality.

Fredrichs (2007) stated that the only way one crime differs from another is in the backgrounds and characteristics of its perpetrators. Most, if not all white-collar offenders are distinguished by lives of privilege, much of it with origins in class inequality. It is estimated that a great deal of white-collar crimes is undetected or if detected, it is not reported. Because of the high status of the perpetrators of these crimes, a highly trained and experienced examiner or investigator is needed to forestall the occurrence of such high profile fraud. This study is anchored on white collar crime theory because it expounds Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments.

Methods

The numerical facts or the data for the investigations consisted of mostly qualitative data primarily acquired through employee interviews. While there was some quantitative data collected, the effectiveness of organizational decisions was based on a 'good, better, best' approach and thus presented itself as qualitative in nature. By definition, case study research is most appropriate when the overall intent is to answer the 'how' and 'why' of specific decisions as related to a contemporary event (Villarreal, 2023). Additionally, flexible design is inherently designed to encapsulate the use of qualitative data (Denny & Weckesser, 2023). In this instance, how the organization is impacted by its leadership's decisions and why those decisions are made, aligned with a single case study method.

Finally, the use of a single case study created a potential baseline wherein other financial and non-financial organizations

can be evaluated, especially considering if the organization was successful in its approach or not. Guetterman and Feters (2018) noted the outcomes of a single case study allow a more effective way to "compare and contrast" (p. 904) the outcomes to other similar firms.

Triangulation is meant to ensure investigation is more defensible and credible (Noble & Heale, 2022). Ultimately, this is done to eliminate bias which may be more prevalent in qualitative data, even though it is applicable across both quantitative and qualitative data sets (Campbell et al., 2020; Noble & Heale, 2019). As it is clear this was mostly qualitative data, the employment of bracketing was meant to minimize as much bias as possible in the data, thus the next logical step was to triangulate data for the purpose of a more effective analysis. While there exists various methodologies for data triangulation, the most effective approach in this case was Racine et al. (2020) demonstrated how data triangulation could be used effectively with both qualitative and quantitative data. By grouping similar concepts from the different datasets and then creating the appropriate protocol for said grouping, they were able to explore any discrepancies/outliers within the data (Racine et al., 2020). As this study's data were derived primarily from in-person interviews using a structured question sheet, it was ideally previously

Organized by 'concept' and thus more easily grouped for triangulation purposes. For example, by collecting quantifiable cost values such as expenditure amounts, the next step was to identify how those figures impacted employee actions. For instance, if it was shown that an employee was unable to share information due to technology limitations, one could review dollar expenditures to determine if the money was allocated and/or spent on the enabling technology. Thus, one can infer that either the expenditure amount was insufficient/non-existent, or the employee did not effectively utilize the technology procured. The culmination of interviews,

follow-on written responses, and limited document reviews resulted in an effective approach for capturing the 'ground truth' of the firms

Results and Discussion

Data collection consisted primarily of interviews of both management and operational personnel within the financial and non-financial firms or organization. The data ranged from descriptive observations, comments made by participants to simple yes/no responses.

The culmination of these different data sets required the employment of various techniques ranging from validation of the participants and the accuracy of responses to the proper alignment of data between both research questions and data types. Ruggiano and Perry (2019) discussed the practice of secondary data analysis which could occur thus emphasizing the importance of properly aligning the data from the beginning. They noted how alignment and accuracy of data is pivotal as there exists the potential for follow up although secondary research lends further credibility, the initial organization and coding of the data is pivotal in determining the initial themes (Nepper & Chai, 2016). What was the process for coding and thus determining emerging themes wherein the research questions could best be addressed? To begin, the main themes were divided into three primary categories: information sharing, investments, and posture assessment. As noted, the data were represented in both comment format and simple yes/no responses. In addition, the overall data collection itself was aligned to ensure the data could be collected against each research theme. For example, within each collected data source (e.g., interview, document review, etc.) there existed specific questions which directly fed the researcher's ability to assess the effectiveness of the organization. However, as this was a qualitative approach, the intent was to evaluate the effectiveness based on outside grading and assessments derived from internal participant observations and experiences

(Kerr et al., 2010). It became imperative to ensure the totality of relevant data collection was achieved, or as could be stated, data saturation wherein all possible relevant data were collected to the point where additional data had no further bearing on analysis. How was this accomplished? As Kerr et al. (2010) noted "data for qualitative analyses can also take many forms, including interviews...observations and documentation" (p. 270).

These were the primary forms of data collected and all the data collected should have directly mapped to the overarching research questions. But how was the data itself represented? As discussed previously, Appendix A and B represented a more structured approach as to how the interviews occurred. As can be seen, the content was meant to align to each of the research questions in both an explanatory format and yes/no format. The coding themes of the combined data entry were then based upon the topic areas defined above.

Similar to Nepper and Chai (2016), the data were transcribed and validated for accuracy and then basic exploratory analysis was conducted to identify any emerging themes in the responses. For example, similar statements made by participants were captured and grouped accordingly and from this, the researcher interpreted the theme being presented. As this is an iterative process, it continued until saturation was achieved. In this case, saturation was noted to be synonymous with thematic saturation and as such, could be seen as "data adequacy" or when no further relevant information could be gleaned; it was determined that enough data were collected to achieve this as most answers were fairly synonymous (Kerr et al., 2010, p. 271). The interview portion of data collection compromised a significant portion of the overall data. As such, it was important to accurately capture responses and to ensure they were properly transferred and binned according to the area of focus.

Some basic quantitative data were required along with the use of basic descriptive statistical analysis, but this was a qualitative study so capturing participant responses was the real key to addressing the research questions. The primary technique used for triangulation was similar to that demonstrated by Racine et al. (2020). As noted, they grouped findings according to concepts (Racine et al., 2020). In this case, the research questions represented three primary categories of data. Table 1 represents the overall general approach to categorizing data. While the overall approach was that of a qualitative case study, there did exist a need for a few quantifiable metrics such as response rates to some of the yes/no questions.

The following hypothesis and respondent statement of fact based on opinion emerges;

HO₁: There is significant effect on organizational performance and of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial and non-financial firms in Africa.

HO₂: There is no relationship between Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments and selection on employees' value adding or turnover and firms performance of financial and non-financial firms in Africa

Once the data were categorized, the data types were reviewed, and the appropriate analysis was applied. For example, there were several questions for all participants related to awareness of recent Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial and non-financial firms in Africa. A simple descriptive statistical process showed the percentage of respondents who were aware of these events. From this, one could then glean whether internal information sharing was effective and whether awareness of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial

and non-financial firms in Africa threats was altering the manner in which the firms operated.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Conclusions

The investigations seeks to address the challenge that many financial and non-financial organizations have, specifically, does there exist investment approaches and information strategies wherein an organization, with limited resources, can still secure itself.

Researchers were very clear, financial and non-financial organizations struggle to defend against cyber-attacks, primarily due to limited resources and personnel (Raineri & Fudge, 2019). While the focus was on investment and information sharing, the core component which ultimately drove the success of the organization was leadership and its commitment to the idea of creating a culture wherein security was a cornerstone principle.

The investigation highlighted multiple challenges, but ultimately, with above 74% of breaches occurring within small- to mid-size organizations, it is clear the organization reviewed was likely to have at least been targeted (Fielder et al., 2021). The study consisted of a qualitative approach wherein various personnel from a smaller organization located in southwest Pennsylvania were interviewed over a 2-week period.

The participants ranged from junior analysts up to the president. The questions ranged from mere assessments of the awareness of various policies to specific questions regarding organizational investments and actions taken in response to well-known cyber events. During this process, it was discovered fairly early that the organization, while limited in number of IT personnel directly responsible for the security of the organization, had not suffered a successful cyber attack in the past 24 months. Furthermore, as was shown

in the analysis, the overall awareness of cyber threats and the organization's ability to send and receive information was rated fairly high.

Therefore, the organization also did not neglect their duty to spend for security and/or IT purchases. While the organization did not have an endless budget, leadership was very clear in that security was a priority and investment and actions would reflect that.

This study makes it clear that a financial organization can defend itself from cyber threat actors. The success of this organization resided in its leadership's commitment to inform its employees of the ongoing nature of the threats they face. Furthermore, leadership was willing to invest as able. As advanced persistent threat actors continue to grow, for an organization to think it does not need to invest in security is ludicrous. However, there still exists no clear metric for determining the optimum amount for each organization. In the end, this is where organizational needs and risk-based approaches may need to ultimately be the driving forces and as such, it is quite possible there will be no uniform approach or metric for cyber security investing. But regardless, the key intangible was that employee awareness coupled with leadership's determination to infuse a culture of security did ultimately pave the way for investments, training, information sharing, and other steps taken wherein the end result was no breaches in the past 24 months.

This study has analyzed why attention has to be given to the question of cyber fraud detection and fraud prevention in Africa, with the aid of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments. The importance of this aspect of accounting cannot be over emphasized as this tool will help in combating fraudulent activities in the councils. No doubt, fraud is an issue that prevents sustainable development in the Africa country and also threatens corporate governance.

Needless to say, it should be noted that the ultimate responsibility for investigating fraud cases rests with Anti-Corruption Agencies, while the prevention and eradication of fraud and corrupt practices rest with the government and management. It is widely known that fraud is not an issue that affects only the public sector, but it is an issue that also affects the private sector and the world at large. This issue of financial fraud is a menace that has led to the collapse of many institutions such as Enron, Worldcom, Lehman brothers etc. Therefore, in order to curb this menace, special attention is required and various mechanisms should be put in place.

That is why Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial and non-financial firms in Africa is a veritable tool in the combating of high level of fraud and corruption.

This study also appreciated some of the reasons why can help in detecting and preventing fraud in the firms across Africa. And other government workers engage themselves in fraudulent practices. Also, the impact of Cyber Forensic Architecture Investments of the financial and non-financial firms in Africa and the basic skills they need to possess to be able to contribute their quota meaningfully in achieving the objectives of this study was extensively discussed not only to excel financial and non-financial firms but to march set progress.

Policy Recommendations

The relevance of forensic accounting in the financial and non-financial firms cannot be over accentuated. The growing level of fraud and other corrupt practices in the financial and non-financial firms sectors in have necessitated the need for cyber Forensic Architecture Investments. It is not new that one of the main focuses of the Buhari Led to Bola Ahmed Tinubu among many other African presidential administration respectively, is to reduce corruption to the barest minimum, yet the issue of fraud cases is still on the high side. Contingent upon several revelations from

the study conducted, there is need to make some policy recommendations, as listed;

1. Based Advised in line with Ramonu (2024). Nigerian's (Africans) people should ignore political instability, economic mismanagement, corruption and other negative factors on Nigeria Africans financial and non-financial economy.
2. The result that emerges the study suggests that the engagement of forensic accountants in Lagos State local governments has significant effect on fraud detection hence more awareness campaign by professional bodies will go a long way to motivate Local governments stakeholders to employ forensic accounting services on regular basis to effectively tackle fraud.
3. Professional bodies providing training and certification in forensic accounting need to restructure and standardize the control of entry procedure in order to adequately regulate entrance into the profession
4. There should be a reward set aside for those who successfully report fraudulent practices after due examination that the report given was authentic and the issue of fraud was duly carried out or was about to be carried out.
5. Employees handling sensitive positions should be rotated after a specific number of years to avoid concealment of fraudulent practices in the firms

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